

**PSYCHO-ACADEMIC VARIABLES AND PERFORMANCE OF
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN
ETCHE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study investigates psycho-academic variables and performance of secondary school students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Ex-post facto design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and three corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 1,586 Senior Secondary Two students (SS 2) drawn from ten public senior secondary schools in the study area. Purposive sampling technique was used to select a sample of 654 SS Two students for the study. "Psycho-Academic Variables Questionnaire" (PAVQ) and "English Language Achievement Test" (ELAT) designed by the researchers were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face validation while test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the instruments, and reliability coefficients of 0.73 and 0.70 were obtained for PAVQ and ELAT, respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions as well as test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. Analysis of data revealed that self-concept and study have a very high positive significant relationship with students' performance in English Language while a very high negative significant relationship was found between test anxiety and students' performance in English Language. Based on these findings, it was recommended, among others, that school guidance counsellors should assist students properly on how to handle and cope with test anxiety for them to be able to reach their full academic potentials.

Keywords: Psycho-academic, variables, performance, students, English Language

Introduction

The increasing cases of poor performance of secondary school students in English Language in internal examinations and in West African Examination Council (WAEC), among others, have continued to be a major concern for the Rivers State Government and other education stakeholders. The situation has become more worrisome considering the fact that a credit in English Language is required for a student to gain admission into any institution of higher learning in Nigeria. In an effort to reverse the trend, the Government of Rivers State adopted a number of interventions targeting students, teachers and the overall teaching and learning environment. Despite these interventions, the performance of students in English Language in the State and particularly in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State continues to dwindle year after year.

Academic performance of students is the centre around which the whole education system revolves. The success and failure of any educational institution is measured in terms of academic performance of students. Not only the schools, but parents also have very high expectations from students with respect to their academic performance, as they believe that better academic results may lead to better career options and future security. Academic performance refers to the knowledge attained and designated by marks assigned by teachers. In educational context, academic performance is the educational goal to be achieved by a student, teacher or institution over a certain period and is measured either by examinations or continuous assessments and the goal may differ from one individual or institution to another. Academic performance is the outcome of education, the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals (Ukaegbu & Inuaeyin, 2023).

It is against this background that the present researchers envisaged that psycho-academic variables could enhance or impede academic performance of secondary school students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State. Psycho-academic variables of interest in this study are self-efficacy, study habit and test anxiety. Self-concept has been, for many years, considered an educationally significant variable that posters the academic performance of the students. Self-concept is the conceptual understanding and persistent regard that sentient beings hold for their existence. In other words, it is the sum total of a person's knowledge and understanding of his or herself. Positive self-concept, for instance, is valued as a goal of education and socialization and is frequently regarded as a potential facilitator of motivation and the achievement of desired outcome such as academic performance. Hence, self-concept attracts countless empirical studies in

and outside Nigeria. For instance, Sanchez and Roda (2017) conducted a study on relationship between self-concept and academic achievement among primary school students. The sample consisted of 245 primary school students currently studying in public or subsidized schools in Almeria Province (Spain). Self-Description Questionnaire was administered to obtain data regarding the subjects' self-concept, and their scholarship performance through marks assigned by their teachers. A close relationship was found between academic self-concept and measures of academic performance. Results indicated that non-academic self-concept negatively predicts school achievement (and that of language, arts and of mathematics), while academic self-concept powerfully and positively predicts both general achievement as well as that in language arts and in mathematics. More so, Adebule (2016) investigated the self-concept and academic performance of students in Mathematics to confirm their relationship. The study also found out whether location of school influenced self-concept of students. A sample of 400 students drawn from four Local Government Areas of Ekiti State was used. The stratified random sampling technique was employed to cater for both urban and rural students. A 25 item instrument called Student Self-Concept Inventory (SSCI) was used. Two hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and t-test statistics. The results of the study showed that self-concept did not influence academic performance of students.

Another variable of interest in this study is study habit. Study habit can be 'good' which means it works and helps students to make good grades - or 'bad' which means it neither work nor help students make good grades. Good study habit includes being organized, keeping good notes and reading textbook, listening in class, and working every day. Bad study habit includes skipping class, not doing work, watching too much TV or playing video games instead of studying, and losing work. Without a good study habit, a student cannot succeed. To succeed, students must be able to appropriately assimilate course content, digest it, reflect on it, and be able to articulate that information in written and/or oral form. Study habit constitutes all the skills and techniques put together in devotion to acquiring proper knowledge, or understanding of learning materials. Good study habit helps the student to develop an inner conviction that he has the ability to practice, retain and recognize learning materials. However, failure to develop that inner conviction results in many students becoming academic casualties, which may not necessarily be attributed to low mental ability, teaching ineffectiveness, or inadequate instructional materials; but to their defective study habits. Eric (2017) is of the view that whenever a student adopts effective study habit, his learning skills, his understanding of learning materials and his memory processing strategies as well as his general performance in academic subjects are improved appreciably.

Based on the importance of study habit in education, Afiahi and Maiyo (2015) conducted a study to determine the relationship between study habit and academic achievement of students. The target population included the 9th standard students at Spicer Higher Secondary School. Stratified random sampling was used to select the respondents, study habits inventory by N.M. Palsane and school examinations records were the main instruments for data collection. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for data analysis. Results of this study revealed a positive relationship of 0.66 between study habit and academic achievement. In a related study, Omotere (2017) investigated the effect of study habit on the academic performance of students using some selected senior secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government Area of Ogun State as a case study. Two hundred (200) students were randomly selected from five senior secondary schools in the area. The instrument utilized for the study was a questionnaire named "Study Habit and Study Attitude Scale" (SHSAS). Four hypotheses were tested and the result showed that study habit has a significant effect on the academic performance of students. More so, the study found out that family background, peer group pressure, personality type of the student and the school environment all affected the reading habit of students in secondary schools.

The third variable which the present researchers envisaged could be linked to the fact that students' academic performance is influenced by test anxiety. Test anxiety is a psychological condition in which people experience extreme stress, anxiety, and discomfort during and/or before taking a test. These responses can drastically hinder an individual's ability to perform well and negatively affect their social, emotional and behavioural development and feelings about themselves and school (Salend, 2015). As well, characteristics of the test environment such as nature of the task difficulty, atmosphere, time constraints, examiner characteristics, mode of administration and physical setting can affect the level of anxiousness felt by the student. A low anxious test taker is able to focus greater attention on the tasks required of him while taking the test, while a high anxious test taker is focused on his internal self, and the anxiety he is feeling. High anxious test takers do not perform adequately on the test as their attention is divided between themselves and test. Therefore, students with high test anxiety are unable to focus their full attention on the test. Furthermore, anxiousness is evoked when a student believes that the evaluative situation, such as an assessment, exceeds his or her intellectual, motivational and social capabilities (Putwain et al., 2016).

Rana and Mahmood (2018) carried out a study on the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of students at the post graduate level using a sample of 414 students randomly selected from seven different science departments in a public sector University in Lahore, Pakistan. Data were collected using the Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI); Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), multivariate statistics and regression analyses were run for data analysis. It was found that a significant negative relationship existed between test anxiety scores and students' achievement scores. The results further showed that a cognitive factor (worry) contributed more in test anxiety than affective factors (emotional). Another study was conducted by Chapell (2015) using a sample of 5,551 undergraduate and graduate students in Pennsylvania and Illinois. The study found a significant difference of academic achievement among three different levels (low, moderate, and high) of test anxiety. For instance, students with low test anxiety had higher academic achievement than students with moderate and higher test anxiety. Similarly, students with moderate test-anxiety had higher academic achievement than students with higher test-anxiety.

Theoretically, this study is anchored on Social Learning Theory propounded by Albert Bandura in 1977. The theory is based on the major premise that behaviour is learned and can be unlearned. Behaviour is in general, a function of one's personality and the environment. Man is born with some innate potentials which the environment conditions. Similarly, one can influence his or her environment using the personality qualities. Consequently, as one interacts in the environment, the adolescents consciously or unconsciously observe and imitate and display behaviour of models. Hence, Bandura posits that there is interrelationship between man's personality, the behaviour and environmental factors. According to Bandura, the entire three elements: The person, the behaviour and the environmental situation are highly interrelated variables, each being capable of influencing the other.

The social learning theory emphasizes the importance of observing and imitating the behaviour, attitudes and emotional reaction of others. Thus, it focuses on learning by observation and imitation. Imitation and modelling of influential persons or models also depend on reinforcement. This reinforcement can either be direct or vicarious. In direct reinforcement, the person imitating the model receives reinforcement directly. When a child, for instance is praised for exhibiting a behaviour, he receives direct reinforcement. In vicarious reinforcement, the person imitating the model does not get reinforced directly. It is rather the model that is reinforced. When one watches a model being reinforced, he is also reinforced indirectly. This is vicarious reinforcement. The motivation to identify with a particular model stems from the fact

that this model possesses a quality which the individual would like to possess. Identification with a model involves the individual taking on observed behaviours, values, beliefs and attitudes of the person with whom he is identifying. Relating it to the present study, adolescents can model their behaviour after their peers who have positive attitudes and behaviour towards education in order to enhance their academic performance.

This theory, if applied to the school, could be an explanation for the seeming relationship that may exist among students' self-concept, study habit, test anxiety and academic performance. The school is a place where students learn by observing the activities that go on in the environment. Effective study habit, how to take tests or exams as well as how to develop personal concept are learnt by students in school. In some cases, students observe such attributes from their teachers and other significant individuals operating in the school environment. All these point to the relevance of Bandura's Social Learning Theory to this present study.

However, from the review of related literature, it was observed that none of the past studies was carried out in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State. Also, it is worthy of note that past researchers focused on Mathematics and other subjects, while the present study was targeted at the performance of public senior secondary school students in English Language. More so, the fact that none of the past researchers used a sample of 654 public senior secondary school students further justified the conduct of this present study. Finally, it was observed that past researchers failed to reach a consensus on the relationship between self-concept, study habit, test anxiety and academic performance of students. Thus, this present study was carried out to fill the identified existing gaps.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between self-concept and performance of secondary school students in English Language?
2. What is the relationship between study habit and performance of secondary school students in English Language?
3. What is the relationship between test anxiety and performance of secondary school students in English Language?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between self-concept and performance of

- secondary school students in English Language.
2. There is no significant relationship between study habit and performance of secondary school students in English Language.
 3. There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and performance of secondary school students in English Language.

Methodology

The *ex-post facto* design was adopted for the study. The *ex-post facto* research design was considered suitable for this study because the researchers did not have direct control over independent variables since they had already occurred. The population of this study consisted of 1586 Senior Secondary Two students (SS 2) drawn from ten public senior secondary schools in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State (Zonal Schools Board, Okehi, 2023). The schools and their respective populations are tabulated below.

S/N	Name of School	Population of Students	Population of SS 2 Students in Each School
1	C.G.S Ikwerre/Etche	1,765	198
2	C.S.S Igbo-Etche	1,995	226
3	C.S.S Egwi Etche	1,487	187
4	C.S.S Umuzoche, Igbodo	598	101
5	C.S.S Ulakwo	1,797	181
6	C.S.S Okoroagu	1,006	121
7	C.S.S Nihi	842	127
8	C.S.S Umuechem	1,368	143
9	C.S.S Odagwa	1,048	129
10	G.S.S Okehi	1,637	173
	Total	13,543	1,586

The researchers selected 654 SS Two students from ten public senior secondary schools in Etche Local Government Area using the purposive sampling procedure to ensure that all the respondents have similar characteristics. The sample of the study represents 44% of the total population of SS Two students from ten public senior secondary schools in the study area.

“Psycho-Academic Variables Questionnaire” (PAVQ) and “English Language Achievement Test” (ELAT) designed by the researchers were used for data collection. PAVQ consisted of three sections and a total of 30 items. Ten (10) items were used to measure each of the academic variables, namely self-concept, study habit and test anxiety. The items were responded to on a four point rating scale of

Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. The second instrument- ELAT consisted of 25 multiple questions in English Language with options A-E. The questions were raised from topics in Senior Secondary Two syllabus. Each question answered correctly was scored 4. Thus the highest score was 100%.

The instrument – PAVQ was face validated by one Professor and one Senior Lecturer in Test and Measurement in the Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, University of Uyo, Uyo, while ELAT was face validated by two English Language teachers in two different secondary schools in the study area. Test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the instruments. Initially, the researchers administered the two instruments on 30 SS Two students who were not part of the study. After two weeks, the researchers re-administered the same copies of the instruments on the same sample. Thereafter, the first and second scores of the respondents were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics and reliability coefficients of 0.73 and 0.70 were obtained for PAVQ and ELAT, respectively. The reliability coefficients were high enough and the instruments were found to be reliable. The instruments were administered on the SS Two students in the sampled schools by the researchers with the help of form masters/mistresses in the sampled schools. The administration of the instruments was carried out after due permission was obtained from the principals of the schools selected for the study. The researchers explained to the students the purpose of the study and the need for them to respond appropriately and honestly. Efforts were made to ensure that all the copies of the instruments were duly filled and collected on the same spot. Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions as well as test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. All data were subjected to analysis by statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 22.

Results

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Self-concept and Performance of Students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State

Variable	n	r	P-value	Remarks
Self-concept	654	0.74	0.003	Sig.
Performance in English				

P<0.05

Table 1 shows the correlation coefficient of 0.74 implying that there is a high positive relationship between students' self-concept and their performance in English Language. This implies that, as students' scores in self-concept increase, there is a corresponding increase in their performance in English Language. More so, test of corresponding hypothesis one shows that the p-value of .003 is significant at 0.05. Thus, hypothesis one is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is retained. This implies that there is a significant relationship between self-concept and performance of students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Study Habit and Performance of Students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State

Variable	n	r	P-value	Remarks
Study Habit				
	654	0.70	0.005	Sig.
Performance in English				

P<0.05

Table 2 shows the correlation coefficient of 0.70 implying that there is a high positive relationship between students' study habit and their performance in English Language. This implies that, as students' scores in study habit increase, there is a corresponding increase in their performance in English Language. More so, test of corresponding hypothesis two shows that the p-value of .005 is significant at 0.05. Thus, hypothesis two is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is retained. This implies that there is a significant relationship between study habit and performance of students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Test Anxiety and Performance of Students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State

Variable	n	r	P-value	Remarks
Test Anxiety				
	654	-0.72	0.001	Sig.
Performance in English				

P<0.05

Table 3 shows the correlation coefficient of -0.72 implying that there is a high negative relationship between students' test anxiety and their performance in English Language. This implies that as students' scores in test anxiety increase, there is a

corresponding decrease in their performance in English Language. More so, test of corresponding hypothesis three shows that the p-value of .001 is significant at 0.05. Thus, hypothesis three is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is retained. This implies that there is a significant relationship between test anxiety and performance of students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of data on research question one revealed that self-concept has a very high positive relationship with students' performance in English Language. This implies that, as students' scores in self-concept increase, there is a corresponding increase in their performance in English Language. This finding is not surprising because a student who sees himself as a success will work hard to achieve success while the reverse will be the case of any student who perceives himself as a failure. More so, test of corresponding hypothesis one showed that there is a significant relationship between self-concept and performance of students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. This present finding agrees with Sanchez and Roda (2017) who in their study, found a close relationship between academic self-concept and measures of academic performance. However, the present study is contradicted by Adebule (2016) whose study showed that self-concept does not influence academic performance of students in Mathematics.

Analysis of data on research question two revealed that study habit has a very high positive relationship with students' performance in English Language. This implies that, as students' scores in study habit increase, there is a corresponding increase in their performance in English Language. This finding is well expected because students who study regularly and effectively are likely to do better academically than their counterparts with poor study habit. More so, test of corresponding hypothesis two showed that there is a significant relationship between study habit and performance of students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. This present finding lends credence to Afiahi and Maiyo (2015) who in their study, found out that there is a positive relationship between study habit and academic achievement of students. However, none of the empirical studies reviewed in this study disagrees with the present finding.

Analysis of data on research question three revealed that there is a high negative relationship between students' test anxiety and their performance in English Language. This implies that, as students' scores in test anxiety increase, there is a corresponding decrease in their performance in English Language. This present

finding could be due to the fact that when a student is tensed and very much anxious, he may lack proper coordination and skills required to do well in a test or examination. More so, test of corresponding hypothesis three showed that there is a significant relationship between test anxiety and performance of students in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. The study is in agreement with Onyeizugbo (2010) who had earlier found that students with higher test anxiety have low academic achievement.

Conclusion

It was concluded that self-concept, study habit and test anxiety are significant contributors to students' performance in English Language in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State. However, while students with positive self-concept as well as those who employ effective study habits are expected to put up good performance academically, the reverse is the case for students with high test anxiety.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. Teachers and indeed all stakeholders must help monitor and supervise students to have private timetable for learning and to guide them in their day-to-day learning since such efforts boost students' academic performance significantly.
2. The teachers should guide students on how to develop good study habits, thereby enhancing their academic success.
3. The school guidance counsellors should assist students properly on how to handle and cope with test anxiety for them to be able to reach their full academic potentials.

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